

CHALLENGES FACED BY NOVICE TRANSLATORS AND INTERPRETERS IN MALAYSIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICES

Dr. MOHAMMED H. ALAQAD

Assistant Professor, Management and Science University (MSU), Malaysia.

Email: alakkadmohmad@yahoo.com

This research has been conducted with funding from the

PALM Strategic Initiatives Centre

ABSTRACT

Despite a long history of interpreting, Malaysia and many other nations are still lagging behind in the evolution of this profession. In fact, interpreting is still regarded as a low-status, semi-professional career that has not yet evolved into a completely professional career due to not fulfilling the requirements of a professional career. The study identifies the challenges and issues faced by novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia and whether these challenges affect their profession or not. The study also highlights the challenges that influence translator identity, which leads to a careful consideration of solutions that might help pave the way for the recognition of translators as respectable professionals in Malaysia. The study made use of a qualitative approach and a structured questionnaire where 27 participants were selected from 3 different institutions, namely, Management and Science University (MSU), University Sains Malaysia (USM), and University Putra Malaysia (UPM). The structured questionnaire has been used as an instrument in this study. The study finds out the main challenges faced by the novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia, including but not limited to; inadequate students' knowledge in translation and interpretation due to the lack of resources, the lack of lecturers and subject experts who hold both academic and industrial expertise in translation and interpreting in the higher education institutions in Malaysia, moreover, the lack of appreciation for the role of translator and interpreter in Malaysian society. The research concludes that a clear relationship between the level of expertise of the subject lecturer and novice translators' or interpreters' challenges was discovered. Such detailed investigations of the relationship would be identified and discussed to provide possible starting points for advanced related studies.

Keywords: translators and interpreters in Malaysia, translator challenges, practical solutions.

1. Introduction

In Malaysia, there has been evidence of translation going back to the earliest Malay cultures. In the 13th and 14th centuries, Muslim missionaries from the Arab world brought Islam to the Malay Archipelago. It was important for translators to translate the numerous theological writings that had been written in Arabic into Malay while the Malay Archipelago was being converted to Islam. During the colonial era, "Hikayat Raja Pasai" and "Hikayat Merong Mahawangsa," two well-known local literary masterpieces, were translated into French and English, respectively, in the year 1849. (Othman, 2007). As a result, Malaya received not just foreign texts through the translation process, but also opened and shared Malay literature with the nations that arrived at its ports first.

"Interpreting" is a term used to refer to the process of rendering a spoken or sign language into another. This is different from the term "translation," which refers to the process of rendering a written text from one language into another. According to Jourdenais & Mikkelson (2015), interpreting is an activity that has been practised since ages. But as a scientific discipline, it is

a relatively new phenomenon. Among the main factors behind the birth of this academic discipline is the effort to transform the practise of interpreting that has been practised for generations into a profession that is officially recognised by society (Boéri, 2015). This transformation process is referred to as professionalization.

Among those requirements is the existence of a body that regulates the practise of interpreting. Australia is one of the leading countries in the professionalisation of interpreting (Hlavac, 2013, 2016; Pym et al., 2013). In Australia, measures to regulate the field of interpreting began as early as 1977 with the establishment of the National Accreditation Authority for Translators and Interpreters, also known as NAATI. The body's function is to set, sustain, and promote high professional standards for the interpreting profession (NAATI, 2018). Currently, Australia is considered the country that holds the most sophisticated and advanced accreditation system in the world (Pym et al., 2013).

2. Background of the Study

Malaysia is regarded as a multilingual and multicultural nation. Malaysian, Chinese (Hokkien, Hakka, Cantonese, etc.), and Indian (Tamil, Gujarati, Malayalam, Panjabi, Sindh, Telugu, etc.) are the three primary mother tongues spoken by the locals of Malaysia (MM2H, 2020). Different languages have been widely used in Malaysia due to the multi-racial, multi-ethnicity of the country. Therefore, the need for translators and interpreters is on the rise, where the necessity becomes crucial whenever conferences, events, seminars are held, or documents are to be handed out. In Malaysia, only a few universities offer translation and interpretation programs, while the rest offer only translation courses in different programs, like TESL, TEFL, and English literature, and those universities mainly focus on teaching theories rather than practices. Therefore, the translation and interpretation courses have been presented to some universities and colleges these days, although not much has been offered in Malaysia. The translation and interpretation professions are not widely known in Malaysia and people tend to consider them superficial due to the fact that they are not getting enough recognition and appreciation like other professions in Malaysian society. The study presumes that students who studied translation and interpreting courses found it hard to focus only on the theoretical part. Instead, if the students get a translation or interpreting assignment where they have to analyze translated articles, news texts, books, or interpret speeches, meetings, or else, they will certainly face several hurdles in the process of rendering these texts or speeches from Malay to English or vice versa due to the scarcity of official translated or interpreted materials from or into the Malay language. Thus, the students are indeed lacking practicality that needs to cover the industrial assignments, market needs, professionalism, and code of ethics. Therefore, this research aims to discuss the challenges and the methods to eradicate them in Malaysia.

2.1 Interpreting Status in Malaysia

The status and career development of interpreters in Malaysia is only discussed by a small number of scholars (Bell & Zubaidah Ibrahim, 1997; Bell, 2007; Leelany Ayob, 2009; Noraini Ibrahim, 2008, 2009; Zubaidah Ibrahim, 2007; Zubaidah Ibrahim-Bell, 2008;) In the meantime, Persatuan Penterjemah Malaysia/Malaysian Translators Association (PPM/MTA), Institut

Terjemahan & Buku Malaysia/Malaysian National Institute of Books and Translation (ITBM), and Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka/Institute of Language and Literature (DBP), are three organisations that have grown to play significant roles in translation work in modern-day in Malaysia. PPM is a national organisation that promotes collaboration and protects the rights of translators. It also offers interested people training, seminars, and courses in translation. By offering translation training and carrying out the work of translating documents from foreign languages into Malay and vice versa, ITBM was established to lead the translation business in Malaysia. PPM often works with ITBM and universities in Malaysia to organise translation events, conferences, and seminars. Yet, the DBP plays a crucial role in developing novel terminologies in Malay and disseminating them so that words from other languages may be matched with Malay terms that are equal. However, none of the above-mentioned associations provide training for interpreters or even organize events, conferences, or seminars to support interpreters. Therefore, an independent and non-profit professional federation known as the Asian Federation of Translators and Interpreters (AFTI) was founded in 2021 in Malaysia on the awareness of the need to establish a federation to serve as an umbrella for all translators, interpreters, and language service providers in Asia, in an effort to promote, protect, and further sustain professionalism among them. It is also stated that the body will be able to fight for and recognize their position internationally, which is considered a significant step forward in paving the way for recognizing this profession regionally and internationally.

3. Problem Statement

The current study aims to find answers to the following questions:

- 1) What are the challenges faced by the junior translators/ interpreters in Malaysia?
- 2) How do these challenges affect the junior translators/ interpreter's profession?
- 3) What are the practical recommendations to overcome these challenges?

4. Literature Review and Conceptual framework

As cultural theories of translation have been expanded, reinforced, and even replaced by linguistic ones, translation has become important to study in its educational, social, and cultural context. This "industrial and cultural revolution" in translation studies (Wang and Munday, 2021; Woodsworth, 1995, pp. 11–12) paved the way for the development of translation histories and practises that demonstrate how translation operations are connected to market demands that cover intellectual, religious, or ideological agendas as the major historical events or movements. The past several decades have seen a sharp rise in the quantity of publications on translation and interpretation. In recent years, the majority of books on translation and interpreting have been "philosophical," concentrating on ideas like translatability, integrity, and the function of translation in literature and culture (Gile, 2009). Though more and more literature on translation and interpretation are turning technical and specialised, concentrating on linguistic, psycholinguistic, terminological, and professional topics.

Although there are many more definitions from various linguistics, all scientists seem to include some of the same things in their formulations. Concept or message comes first, followed by symbol or language (SL and TL), and then the process or action, this definition is proposed by the several translation scholars such as Bell (1991), Sager (1994), Darwish (2003), the steps in the translation process, etc. Instructors should also teach the various strategies and approaches which translators can apply while translating to ensure faster and more accurate translation products. Furthermore, terminology must also be taught. Instructors should guide their student to work hard to improve themselves in at least 3 languages in which they wish to use while translating and to improve on their subject matter in case they choose to translate academic texts such as science, technology, history etc. to ensure that the content is not distorted or made ambiguous during the translation process.

The present study is likely one of the few research studies looking at the challenges junior translators in Malaysia experience and how those challenges have influenced their profession. Only a few papers that shed light on the translation and interpreting profession in Malaysia in relation to the translator's status and self-perception in Malaysia were discovered by the researcher after a thorough review of the pertinent literature that was available for this study. These papers were written by Kang, M. S., & Shunmugam, K. (2014). The researcher examined the status of translators in Malaysia in regard to their line of work. Kang and Shunmugam arrived at the following conclusion: "Although Malaysian translators saw themselves as professionals in society, customers and the general public do not. As obstacles that substantially damage the standing of their professions, the translators also noted unfair competition from amateur translators and unethical behaviours in their industry caused by a lack of a code of ethics." (2014).

Noraini Ibrahim was a second researcher who carefully researched the field of interpreting in Malaysia (2007). She questioned the interpreting field in Malaysia in her PhD thesis, Conference Interpreting in Malaysia, on the basis that there aren't enough qualified interpreters working there, making entry into the field quite simple. According to Zubaidah (2004), regrettably, the market for language service providers in this country (Malaysia) is chaotic and uncontrolled, allowing anybody to set themselves up as an interpretation or translator. Language service providers are not subject to the same rules that apply to the medical and legal professions on admission, retention, and member behaviour. The possibility that meaning can- and may-be distorted by translators and interpreters, whether on purpose or accidentally, is a persistent worry. A code of ethics is therefore a prerequisite. Almost minimal formal training is provided to the Malaysian interpreter.

5. Conceptual framework

In order to properly guide this research, it is necessary to establish a framework with an operationalized definition of the term 'profession', as it will specify the particular areas or elements which the study attempts to investigate. The elements found in the conceptual framework for this research are constructed based on the common elements of what constitutes a profession which was included mainly in the definitions by Grossman (2002), McConnell

(2004), Godbout (2009), and Mishra (2012). There is a total of 7 elements that set the parameter for this study which aims to investigate the translation profession in Malaysia.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of this study

Figure 1 presents the 7 elements identified in the study, which together comprise the features of a profession. The phenomenon investigated in this study is the professionalization of the translation profession in Malaysia, which is described via a comparative analysis focused on these 7 elements. The findings of the study will then be used to determine the phase of professionalization according to Tseng's model, and subsequently, this study aims to offer a modified model that can be used to describe the professionalization process of the translation profession, in particular.

In brief, the 7 elements needed for every type of profession are: status, prestige, and remuneration; education and training; professional association; code of ethics; use of quality standards; and lastly, Continuing Professional Development (CPD). The status of any profession is determined by its position in a given society and the extent to which the members

of that profession can easily be replaced. For example, in Malaysia, the social status of the profession is low because it is not as well-known as other professions like medical. However, the members are not easily replaced because there are not many people who pursue this field, so the need is high. Therefore, the fees in Malaysia are relatively high due to the high demand for translators as Malaysia is a multi-racial country. It shows that the difference in remuneration is affected by the demand for a translator. Not to forget, as a translator, education is one of the unchangeable elements necessary for the creation of a professional translator. The competency of a translator is based on how thorough the education and training the translator has gotten. In most countries, the professional of a translator is based on academic qualifications, though working experience is an advantage. The Malaysian Translators' Association (MTA) is the representative body of translators in Malaysia. Those who wish to join hands with them must possess a qualification at least in a certificate, a diploma, or a degree in translation. Although MTA is known as Malaysia's leading translation association, the current state and major issues of the translation profession are that there is no licensing system, no code of ethics that is clearly defined or enforced on association members, and no use of quality standards. Hence, there is a distinct need for private agents to improve the translation profession in a way that the MTA can't. The fifth element is the code of ethics, also known as a code of conduct, is a principle, values, standards, or rules of behaviour that guide the decisions, procedures, and systems of an organisation in a way that (a) contributes to the welfare of its key stakeholders, and (b) respects the rights of all constituents affected by its operations, as defined by the International Federation of Accountants or IFAC (2019: 6). Codes of ethics vary by profession, and it is critical for all members to adhere to them closely because their level of professionalism is determined by their ability to meet the quality standard of their client. This standard provides clients with a lucid definition of the procedures, requirements, and outcomes of the service. Meeting the standard means that the translation service rendered has fulfilled the market's satisfactory level.

Lastly, continuing professional development (CPD) is a significant component in every known profession these days. Madden and Mitchell (1993/2018) define professional development as the process of maintaining and enhancing the knowledge, expertise, and competence of professionals throughout their careers. From a translation point of view, it is convenient for professional translators to engage in CPD if they are to remain professionally competent with a competitive edge. The elements explained above are important in a way that students can investigate their profession ahead of time, as these elements are common for every profession in this world.

6. Methodology

Where teaching translation is concerned, the University of Science Malaysia (also known as Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM) and Universiti Putra Malaysia (Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM)) are the sole tertiary institutions in the country that offer a discipline specialising in translation and interpretation up to the doctoral level. Apart from USM and UPM, University Malaya (UM), Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (The National University of Malaysia (UKM)), Management and Science University (MSU), and a few other universities and colleges are also

offering some translation programmes or featuring translation subjects in other programs. The current research study made use of a qualitative approach and structured questionnaire were 27 participants selected from 3 different institutions, namely, Management and Science University (MSU), University Sains Malaysia (USM), and University Putra Malaysia (UPM). A method of data collection involving the use of questionnaires is delivered to translators to elicit responses to a number of closed and open-ended questions related to the research. Statistics which can describe certain core aspects of the translation profession were derived via this method.

No.	Organisation	No. of Participants
1	Management and Science University (MSU)	11
2	University of Science (USM)	15
3	University Putra Malaysia (UPM)	1
Total		27

Table 3.1: Participants

7. Data Analysis and Discussion

The total number of respondents that have been collected is 27.

Part A of the questionnaire: about the demographic profile, 88.9% of the students were female and only 11.1% were male. In addition, those who filled up the form were 44.4% undergraduate students while 40.7% were diploma students. The remaining 14.8% were graduates and post-graduate students, with both 7.4% each. Most of those junior translators were 21–25 years old, with 48.1%. 29.6% of them were aged 17–20 years old, and 22.3% were 26 years and above. As the questionnaire was distributed in Malaysia, of course more than half of the respondents were Malays, while 18.5% were Chinese, 11.1% were Indians. From these 27 respondents, 12 of them were from private universities, which is Management and Science University (MSU), while the remaining 15 are from public universities, which are University Science Malaysia (USM) and University Putra Malaysia (UPM). Lastly, question 7 from Part A of the questionnaire was about the years of study, where 51.9% were in year 2, 29.6% in year 4, and 18.5% are in their first year. Below are the graphs in a pie chart form.

What is your gender?
27 responses

What is your level of education level in translation and interpretation?
27 responses

Part B of the Questionnaire: it collects opinions from the novice translators/interpreters about the translation and interpretation challenges they face in Malaysia. The first 6 questions were yes/no question (yes: blue, no: red) while the next 3 questions, students have to choose between never (blue), sometimes (red) or often (orange). Also, question 10 and 11 are questions with multiple choices of answers. Another 5 questions are an agree (blue) and disagree (red) type of question and the remaining 4 of the questions from the questionnaire were to collect the opinions that consist of various answers. Below are the graphs in a pie chart form.

Do you think the profession of translation and interpretation is getting enough exposure in Malaysia?
27 responses

Based on the chart above, 24 of the respondents agreed that translation and interpretation profession did not get enough exposure and recognition while 3 of them disagreed with the statement.

All 27 of the respondents believed that there are barely institutions that offers translation and interpretation courses in Malaysia.

Books, articles and documents regarding translation and interpretation course are hard to find in Malaysia.

27 responses

The result shows that 74.1% of the respondents voted yes that translation and interpretation books, article and documents are hard to find in Malay language while 25.9% believe that they still can access some of these materials with some difficulty.

Based on question 6, 51.9% voted no about translation and interpretation students mainly study based on theories and lack practices while 48.1% voted yes. This is probably because different universities have different methods of teaching.

Students in this course, mainly study based on the theory rather than practice.

27 responses

During translation practices, do you look for the equivalence in dictionaries?

27 responses

Question no. 8 is about how often junior translators refer to dictionary. As a result, we can see that most of them seek assistance from dictionary while the rest only use dictionary a few times while doing their translation task.

Have you seen any advertisement on translation and interpretation services in any of the following;
27 responses

Followed by the previous topic, this question is also regarding translation and interpretation advertisement. We can conclude that translation and interpretation profession indeed does not get enough recognition in Malaysia since the advertisements are frequently seen only in online websites. Sadly, 8 of the respondents have never seen any of it.

Institutions in Malaysia should take the initiative to promote this course.
27 responses

Moving on to the next type of questions where they can only choose between agree and disagree answer. Although 1 of them disagreed with the statement, the rest of the respondents agreed that universities and colleges in Malaysia should promote this course widely. This way, many students will be interested to join the course. Only then translation and interpretation profession can survive in Malaysia.

Translation process in Malaysia takes longer time due to the lack of resources.
27 responses

Due to the low recognition of translation and interpretation in Malaysia, the translation process in Malaysia takes longer time because there are not much professional equipment and resources for translators to do their work. Based on this statement, 66.7% agreed while 33.3% disagreed. The A and B languages are both translator's active language where A language is the translator's mother tongue language and B language is a language that the translator fluent in.

Having A and B languages is enough for students.
27 responses

However, by only knowing the 2 languages, 70.4% of the respondents believed that it is not enough while 29.6% voted the opposite.

The last 4 questions (no.17-20) where the respondents have to state their own opinion. Therefore, no chart or graph are available. Instead, the answers from all 27 responses will be discussed one by one.

7.1 Discussion of Findings in Relation to Research Questions

A number of key findings are discussed in the above sections. Here, the findings will be discussed in relation to the three research questions which reflect the research objectives that the current study aims to achieve: (1) identify the challenges faced by novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia, (2) determine how these challenges affect the translators and

interpreters' profession in Malaysia, and (3) suggest a practical recommendation to overcome these challenges.

Discussion of Findings in Relation to Research Questions 1. What are the challenges faced by novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia?

According to most respondents, the challenges faced by novice translators and interpreters include the inadequate lecturer's knowledge of translation and interpretation; the lack of teachers; resources and learning materials available in the core subjects of translation and interpreting; the limited opportunities of industrial linkage and practical experience in translation and interpreting; the difficulty of translating culturally specific terms between English and Malay, the lack of working memory for interpreters, the paucity of using note-taking skills, the difficulty in interpreting idiomatic and cultural words, and puns, as well as the lack of self-awareness and linguistic sensitivity.

The second most challenging part is being a novice translator and interpreter, where it is hard to find jobs and connect with clients because it is believed that novice translators and interpreters lack practicality and require more time to learn the tactics of professionalism and market needs.

Discussion of Findings in Relation to Research Questions 2. How do these challenges affect the novice translators/ interpreter's profession in Malaysia?

It is believed that translation and interpretation is a measly profession in Malaysia that does not get enough recognition from the public. Due to that, translators and interpreters feel that their roles are not well appreciated as they lack the required training, preparation, and support from the community. Also, the lack of regulations to protect the rights of translators and interpreters has caused intrusive individuals from other professions to freely compete with trained and novice translators and interpreters for their jobs, as they believe that the translation profession is a profession for those who do not have a profession. This is accompanied by public opinion that thinks lowly of translator skills. Hence, they do not capture the need to engage a trained translator or interpreter to do the job, as they believe anyone who speaks the language can translate it. On the other hand, translation clients and agencies prefer to hire translators who offer the lowest rate regardless of their background, expertise, or quality. Thus, they compromise quality for quantity in order to cut costs and increase profit.

Discussion of Findings in Relation to Research Questions 3. What are the practical recommendations to overcome these challenges?

Few scholars have addressed the status of translators and interpreters in Malaysia (Bell & Zubaidah Ibrahim, 1997/2007; Bell, 2007/2008; Leelany Ayob, 2009; Noraini Ibrahim, 2008, 2009;). Unfortunately, Malaysia's market for language services is chaotic and uncontrolled, making it possible by anyone calling themselves an interpreter or translator to practise their profession. Language service providers are not subject to the same rules that govern admission, membership, and code of conduct in the other disciplines like medicine and law.

Thus, the researcher believes that it is a necessity to provide practical recommendations in the following list to overcome these challenges:

On the individual level:

1. Novice translators and interpreters should practice more translation and interpreting assignments and learn new languages.
2. Novice translators and interpreters should promote themselves to the community online and offline and become active in their profession on social media.
3. Novice translators and interpreters should keep up with learning new skills related to their profession, keep learning continuously, and read technical books and articles.
4. Enhance their memory skills and note taking skills thru training and workshops.
5. Novice translators and interpreters should participate and exchange knowledge with their peers in translation and interpreting events, conferences, and seminars, and apply for institutional memberships and get certified.
6. Connect and network with others in the field through social media and other platforms.
7. On the government level:
8. Promote the translation and interpreting markets.
9. Control the market of language service providers and ensure that they operate under an official and regulated market.
10. Support for professional events, conferences, training sessions, and workshops.
11. Provide grants and funds for research and publications to increase awareness of the importance of this profession.
12. Create linkages and connections between academia and industry in this profession.
13. Increase the rate of employability for translators and interpreters in the market.
14. Provide funds and impose rules on the translation and interpreting associations to hire and train novice translators and interpreters and prepare them for the market.
15. Connect between the academic graduation rate and the market needs in order to cover the gap by opening new positions that accommodate the graduates of this profession in the market.
16. Request the translation and interpreting associations to produce more glossaries and materials in print and online.
17. Ensure that the universities that provide translation and interpreting have the required labs and software and provide workshops for the students.

8. Conclusion

The research findings show that a profession truly becomes established when it reaches stage 4. However, it is proven that the translation profession in Malaysia is still at stage 2, which means that we still have a long way to go. Consequently, the need for suggestions for future improvement of the profession in Malaysia is crucial.

The current study sheds light on the challenges faced by novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia. The study is worthy of attention because it explains the dominant challenges in underling the issues of low respect and recognition of this profession. Besides, the study is significant since it has proven a practical recommendation to tackle the challenges faced by novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia. However, a limitation of this study is that the numbers of participants were relatively small, compared with the total number of novice translators and interpreters in Malaysia.

References

1. Al Aqad, M. H. (2017). Challenges and Suggested Solutions of Teaching Translation at Gaza Strip Universities (Palestine). *Arabic Language, Literature & Culture*, 2(2), 34-39.
2. Ayob, L. (2009). The Visibility of translators and interpreters in Malaysia. *The Sustainability of the Translation Field*, 272.
3. Bell, R. T. (1991). *Translation and Translating*, London.
4. Bell, R. T., & Ibrahim, Z. (1997). Commonplace and indispensable; the interpreter in the new reality. In *Language in Development: Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Language in Development* (pp. 23-36).
5. Bell, R.T. (2007). Alternative Futures for a National Institute of Translation: A Case Study from Malaysia. In C. Wadensjö, B. Englund Dimitrova, & A.L. Nilsson (Eds.). *The Critical Link 4*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
6. Boéri, J. (2015). Key internal players in the development of the interpreting profession. In *The Routledge handbook of interpreting* (pp. 41-56). Routledge.
7. Darwish, A. (2003). *The Transfer Factor: Selected essays on translation and cross-cultural communication*. Writescop Publishers.
8. Godbout, M. (2009, August). Is translation a profession? In Hasuria Che Omar, Haslina Haroon and Aniswal Abdul Ghani (Eds.), *The Sustainability of the Translation Field*. Paper presented at the 12th International Conference on Translation, Malaysian Translators' Association – Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, 18-20 August (pp.519-531). Kuala Lumpur: Malaysian Translators Association.
9. Godbout, M. (2013, August). A Credentialing Approach for the Recognition of Translators Professional Competencies. Paper presented in the 14th International Conference on Translation, Penang, Malaysia.
10. Grossman, A. (2002). Exploring professional values for the 21st century. Is professionalization always to be desired? Retrieved November 1, 2013, from <http://www.thersa.org/acrobat/Grossman.pdf>
11. Hlavac, J. (2013). A cross-national overview of translator and interpreter certification procedures. *Translation & Interpreting*, The, 5(1), 32-65.
12. Hlavac, J. (2016). Interpreter credentialing, testing and training in Australia: past, contemporary and future directions. *FITISPos International Journal*, 3, 59-81.

13. https://www.naati.com.au/media/2195/naati_annual_report_2018-web.pdf
14. Ibrahim, N. (2007). Interpreting in Malaysia: An Overview. *Puentes*, 7(October 2007), 89.
15. Ibrahim, N. (2008). Conference interpreting in Malaysia: Professional and training perspectives.
16. Ibrahim, N. (2009). Parliamentary Interpreting in Malaysia: A case study. *Meta: journal des traducteurs/Meta: Translators' Journal*, 54(2), 357-369.
17. Kang, M. S. (2015). A comparative study of the translation profession in Malaysia and Korea/Kang Myoung Sook (Doctoral dissertation, University of Malaya).
18. **Kang, M. S., & Shunmugam, K. (2014). The translation profession in Malaysia: the translator's status and self-perception. *GEMA Online® Journal of Language Studies*, 14(3).**
19. Kim, M., Munday, J., Wang, Z., & Wang, P. (Eds.). (2021). *Systemic Functional Linguistics and translation studies*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
20. Management & Science University (2022). Diploma in Translation and Interpreting. Accessed on 30 March 2022 from <https://www.msu.edu.my/diploma-translation-and-interpreting>
21. McConnell, S. (2004). *Professional software development*. New York: Addison-Wesley.
22. Mikkelsen, H., & Jourdenais, R. (Eds.). (2015). *The Routledge handbook of interpreting* (p. 30-44). New York: Routledge.
23. Mishra, L. (2012). Is financial planning advisory evolving as a new profession in India? *Asian Journal of Research in Banking and Finance*, 2 (6), 99-121.
24. NAATI (2018). *National Accreditation Authority for Translators and Interpreters Annual Report*
25. Noraini Ibrahim. (2009). Parliamentary interpreting in Malaysia: A Case Study. *Meta: Translators' Journal*. 54(2), 357-369.
26. Othman, M.S. (2007). Contributions of translation activities in Malay, Chinese and Indian civilization. *Tajarub wa Khibrat Wa Mashari'wa Taqniyat fi al-Tarjamah*, 387-391.
27. Pym, A., Grin, F., Sfreddo, C., & Chan, A. L. (2013). *The status of the translation profession in the European Union*. Anthem Press.
- Kang, M. S., & Shunmugam, K. (2014). The translation profession in Malaysia: The translator's status and self-perception. *GEMA Online Journal of Language Studies*, 14(3).
28. Russell, D., & Hale, S. (2008). *Interpreting in legal settings*. Gallaudet University Press.
29. Sager, J. C. (1994). *Language engineering and translation: consequences of automation* (Vol. 1). John Benjamins Publishing.
30. Tseng, J. (1992). Interpreting as an emerging profession in Taiwan. A sociological model. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Fu Jen Catholic University, Taiwan.